

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Project Website and Social Media Platforms

Work Package 7, Deliverable D7.5

Project Website and Social Media Platforms

Work package 7, Deliverable D7.5

Please refer to this report as follows:

Vuckovic, M., Kozłowska, A., (2023). Project website and social media platforms. Deliverable D7.5 of the Horizon Europe project REENGAGE.

Project information	
Project name:	REENGAGE – Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
Grant Agreement No.	101086530
Start date:	01/01/2023
Duration:	36 months
Coordinator:	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology Giefinggasse 4, 1210 Vienna, Austria
Contact:	Jan Peters-Anders, Research Engineer
	Funded by the European Union GA n° 101086530.
Deliverable details	
Description:	This deliverable provides a short description of the REENGAGE website structure and the social media channels. The links to these dissemination assets are also provided.
Version:	Final
Dissemination level:	PU (Public)
Due date:	30/06/2023
Submission:	29/06/2023
Lead:	VRVis Zentrum für Virtual Reality und Visualisierung Forschungs-GmbH
Author(s):	Vuckovic, M. (VRVis Zentrum für Virtual Reality und Visualisierung Forschungs-GmbH), Austria Kozłowska, A. (Austrian Institute of Technology), Austria

Legal Disclaimer

All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user, therefore, uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the authors' view.

Users wishing to reuse material from this work that is attributed to a third party, such as tables, figures or images, are responsible for determining whether permission is needed for that reuse and for obtaining permission from the copyright holder. The risk of claims resulting from infringement of any third party-owned component in the work rests solely with the user.

© 2023 by REENGAGE Consortium

Table of Contents

Content

1	GREENGAGE summary.....	2
2	Description of the Dissemination Assets.....	3
2.1	GREENGAGE website	3
2.2	Social Media	3

List of Figures

Figure 1:	Structure of project GREENGAGE.....	2
Figure 2:	Section of the landing page of the GREENGAGE website.	3

Executive summary (publishable)

This deliverable provides a short description of the REENGAGE website structure and the social media channels. The links to these dissemination assets are also provided.

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to promote innovative governance processes, and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project will leverage citizens' participation and equip them with innovative digital solutions that will transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens will be inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The aim is to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This will be facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories will be a place where pilot cities will co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up process with top-down perspectives. This will provide the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aims to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The envisioned citizens observatory campaigns will be deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which will complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Description of the Dissemination Assets

2.1 GREENGAGE website

www.greengage-project.eu

The GREENGAGE website is a core communication and dissemination medium ensuring international visibility, communication, and promotion activities. The website outlines the scope, objectives, the involved partners, activities, and provides regular updates on the general progress of the project. The website structure reflects the requirements of the project while maintaining user-friendly interface and navigation. It is divided into 6 sections:

- Project (introduction to GREENGAGE)
- About us (information about consortium and partners)
- Pilots (helps to navigate through the pilots, holds information on each use case)
- Resources (place holder for deliverables, publications, newsletter, multimedia)
- Events (calendar with all previous and planned events engaging GREENGAGE)
- GREENGAGE Toolbox (placeholder for directing to the demo platform)

Figure 2: Section of the landing page of the GREENGAGE website.

2.2 Social Media

GREENGAGE will be spreading its messages and updates over Twitter and LinkedIn. These channels will serve as accelerators to the discussion aligned with project objectives and activities and will further serve as potential scouting medium for a widespread engagement.

Twitter account is @GREENGAGEproject. The link to the account is:

https://twitter.com/GREENGAGE_EU

LinkedIn account is www.linkedin.com/company/greengage-project/.